

REPEATED SLAMMING OF FOAM CORE SANDWICH COMPOSITE PANELS ON WATER

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SUMMARY

Repeated slamming indicated greater accumulation of damage accompanied by lower lifetimes as a function of increasing slamming energy or lower deadrise angle. Slamming energy vs lifetime curves showed an exponentially decreasing trend. Catastrophic failure resulted from a major crack formation near the chine or the keel depending on the deadrise angle.

Keywords: repeated slamming, damage

SLAMMING

Observations of slamming phenomena on actual ships indicate a violent and repetitive impact of ship bottoms on the water. The high stiffness, light weight and energy absorption gives the sandwich composites an advantage over conventional alloys used in the marine industry [1]. As most modern day marine craft operate at high speeds subjected to repeated wave slamming loads, the prediction of safe operational life is of paramount importance especially in newly developed sandwich composite ship hull structures [1]. Abundant literature is available on the wave slamming of ship hulls on water, however, most of the work is limited to one-strike impact and focus of discussion is primarily the peak pressures, being the key design parameter [2-4]. This research offers unique and extensive data on the foam core sandwich composite lifetime characteristics subject to repeated slamming. A methodology is also proposed and implemented to assess cumulative damage during slamming.

Material and Testing Methodology

Damage under repeated slamming generally initiates and accumulates in the foam core along the interface, leaving facesheets intact and free of anomalies until catastrophic failure, that makes the detection a challenging task [1,5]. Discrete strain and pressure information or data obtained from acoustic emission, etc. fail to provide reliable in-situ damage information under repeated slamming [2]. A comparative flexural fatigue analysis was implemented in the current study in order to assess the cumulative damage suffered during the slamming process.

The sandwich composite used was composed of 96kg/m^3 polyurethane foam and $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_1$ carbon fiber facesheets bonded to the core with a 600cps epoxy resin. Specimens were fabricated using VARTM process. Sandwich panels of $25.4\text{cm} \times 20.2\text{cm} \times 12.5\text{mm}$ dimensions were mounted on a wedge shaped specimen holder and dropped freely from various heights. The slamming energy was defined as the kinetic energy of the free falling assembly just before the impact with the water. The specimens had roller supports on two sides and were free at the keel and the chine (Figure 1). Test samples were subjected to repeat slamming at various slamming energy levels between 160-780J and deadrise angles ranging from 0° to 45° .

Figure 1: Test Setup and Specimen details

Results

Single Slamming: Higher slamming energy and lower deadrise angle lead to greater accumulated damage in the specimen, as seen in Table 1. As anticipated, a decrease in β and an increase in E increases the probability of failure, that is in accord with the principle of conservation of momentum and trends reported in the literature [2,3].

Table 1: Single slamming results

Slamming Energy, E_n (J)	Deadrise Angle (β)			
	0°	15°	30°	45°
161	20%	0%	0%	0%
269	100%	0%	0%	0%
386	100%	0%	0%	0%
511	100%	67%	0%	0%
642	100%	100%	0%	0%
779	100%	100%	33%	0%

In order to circumvent the mathematical difficulties associated with the effect of hydroelasticity, an analytical hydroelasticity coefficient was developed using FEA, as provided in Equation 1 below,

$$\mu_H = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{exp}}}{\epsilon_{r/q-s}} = 1 - \eta \left[\left(\frac{2E_n}{m} \right)^{1/2} \frac{1}{V_s} \right] \quad (1)$$

where η is an experimentally adjusted parameter and E_n , m and V_s correspond to the slamming energy, mass of the free falling apparatus and wave propagation velocity, respectively. $\epsilon_{\text{exp}}/\epsilon_{r/q-s}$ refers to the ratio of the experimental strain to the strain obtained using rigid quasi-static assumption. Using this hydroelasticity into a quasi-static analysis of a simply supported panel subject to uniformly distributed pressure (taken from Wagner's theory [6]) yielded the following peak strain expression:

$$\epsilon = \mu_H \frac{\rho_w b z \pi^2 L^2 E_n}{16mD \tan(\beta)} \quad (2)$$

here β is the deadrise angle, L is the span length, b is the width of the specimen and z is the distance from the neutral axis and ρ_w is the density of the water. The stiffness of the sandwich composite is given as [25],

$$D = E_f \frac{bt_f^3}{6} + E_f \frac{bt_f d^2}{2} + E_c \frac{t_c c^3}{12} \quad (3)$$

here t_f and t_c correspond to the thickness of the facesheet and the core, respectively, whereas E_f and E_c correspond to the modulus of elasticity of the facesheet and foam core. Without including the effect of hydroelasticity (μ_H), the strains were grossly overestimated especially at higher slamming energies, however, the comparison

between experimental and theoretical strains improved dramatically when a hydroelasticity function μ_H (Eq. 1) was introduced in Eq. 2, as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Peak experimental strains compared with Equation 1

Modes of failure under single slamming corresponded primarily to core shear and interface failure, as seen in Figure 3. Catastrophic failure occurred with the facesheet rupture.

Figure 3: Modes of failure under single slam

Repeated Slamming: A gradually decreasing lifetime was observed as a function of increasing slamming energy or decreasing deadrise angle, as seen in the average values plotted on a logarithmic scale in Figure 4. E/E_n along the ordinate in these graphs represents the percentage of energy required for catastrophic failure under single slams at each deadrise angle β . A comparison with flexure fatigue life is also presented in Figure 4 that shows a striking disparity with the slamming lifetimes and the effect of the rate and type of loading. Under repeated slamming, none of the specimens failed at 45° deadrise angle up to the 2000 cycle threshold. An enormous scatter in the lifetime data was also observed with up to an order of magnitude difference in lifetimes under same testing conditions. It is no uncommon to observe large scatter in the lifetime data under fatigue, impact and even static loading conditions [7-10].

Figure 4: E-N curves compared with the S-N curve

Figure 4 also indicates decreasing slopes as a function of increasing deadrise angles, i.e., corresponding to an increase in life. These slopes plotted against the deadrise angle as shown in Figure 5 can form the basis of safe design and operational conditions. It is proposed that failure is more likely to occur below this curve, whereas specimens are prone to failure outside of this region (Figure 5). ϵ_u in Figure 5 represents the threshold strain causing catastrophic failure under single slam (~ 0.0035). These observations are in accordance with the theoretical formulations present in the literature that indicate a gradual but significant reduction in peak pressures at higher deadrise angles [1], thus it is not surprising why failure is unlikely beyond a 30° deadrise angle.

Figure 5: Safe operational conditions

Damage detection in real time under slamming is a challenging task due mainly to instrumentation limitation. For example, discrete pressure data does not offer any reliable damage information. Strain gages, on the other hand, have been widely used in damage assessment, however, mostly under quasi-static conditions or under single slamming scenario [1,7,10,11]. Whereas, the use of strain gages under truly dynamic and repeated impact reveals many shortcomings, such as, i) the highly discrete nature of the data makes the comparison between specimens subjective, ii) the strain gauges under repeated slamming fatigue themselves, thus giving rise to the cyclic noise and necessitating frequent recalibration during the testing, iii) it is difficult to keep the gauges isolated from water under repeated slamming, therefore, short circuiting becomes an issue that forces sporadic test interruptions to replace the strain gauges.

In the absence of viable real time damage detection instrumentation, various tests were interrupted at about 50% of the average repeated slamming life, the specimens were cut along the dashed lines indicated in Figure 1 and tested in flexural mode under fatigue loading to ascertain damage accumulated under repeated slamming. A substantial reduction in life was observed as compared with non-slammed specimens (Figure 6). The loss of life parameter was used to assess accumulated damage in the material under repeated slamming.

Figure 6: Post slamming fatigue lifetimes

Curiously, the damage accumulation and onset of failure was observed to occur near the chine for 0° and 15° whereas the damage and failure shifted towards the keel at 30° deadrise angle. On the contrary, greater reduction in fatigue life consistently occurred in specimens corresponding to the keel zone as opposed to the chine zone irrespective of the deadrise angle, thus clearly indicating greater accumulation of damage near the keel under repeated slamming. The complicated micromechanisms that cause the counter intuitive shift in damage accumulation from keel to the chine as a function of deadrise angle can not be completely understood unless damage can be monitored in-situ during slamming, which is currently the main limitation. However, it should be noted that the ship design is primarily based on peak pressure measurements that are always experienced near the keel under free drop conditions with the presumption that the critical damage must coincide with the same location, as evidenced by several theoretical and experimental studies [1-4]. The results obtained currently are therefore quite relevant in terms of practical design and analysis.

Failure under repeated slamming generally occurred as a result of core tearing along the interface and subsequent core shear. Even though the slamming loads were almost uniformly distributed and the resulting damage was widespread, a single major crack was observed to form under repeated slamming localized near the chine or the keel depending on the deadrise angle that lead to the catastrophic failure, as seen in Figure 7. Catastrophic failure occurred due to facesheet separation caused by a rapid growth of interfacial core tearing. Under slamming, there was no evidence to suggest any facesheet damage prior to catastrophic failure.

For post slamming fatigue specimens, modes of failure were predominantly core shear accompanied by local buckling of the facesheet, whereas, the modes of failure under fatigue of non-slammed specimens pointed exclusively to core shear with no evidence of facesheet buckling, thus indicating damage accumulation at the interfaces and facesheets under slamming. Even though the specimens cut near the keel showed a marked reduction in fatigue life as compared to the chine, the modes of failure were nearly identical.

Figure 7: Failure site near the chine or the keel depending on the deadrise angle

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